

ACCEPTANCE TEST REQUIREMENTS FOR THE PROCUREMENT
OF
ELECTROSTATIC DISCHARGE (ESD) PROTECTIVE WORKSTATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on test methods developed by the Aerospace Guidance and Metrology Center (AGMC) at Newark AFB for determining the acceptability of Electrostatic Discharge (ESD) protective workstations. Prior to this effort, no government specifications or standards for the procurement of ESD protective workstations or any other ESD control items existed. The lack of specifications for ESD Control products has left government personnel at the mercy of the ESD control product manufacturer as to whether effective products are received. MIL-W-87893, "Workstation, Electrostatic Discharge (ESD) Control" is the first specification developed by AGMC that has been published as a military standard. It specifies resistance requirements, static decay values, and general construction requirements for static control workstations and their components for use in applications where the protection of ESD sensitive items is required.

INTRODUCTION

The ESD Control Workstations outlined in MIL-W-87893 consist of three major components; (1) the worksurface, (2) an adjustable wrist strap, and (3) a common point ground system (CPGS). The worksurfaces have been broken down into three types for use in three different situations. Type I worksurfaces are rigid and designed for use in Clean Room applications. Type II worksurfaces are cushioned and flexible and can be used in all applications other than clean rooms where static sensitive devices are handled. Type III worksurfaces are smaller and flexible and are to be used where normal ESD Control workstations cannot be installed, such as when doing remote aircraft maintenance or when servicing test equipment. Preconditioning and cleaning are necessary prior to conducting acceptance testing on worksurface samples. Testing consists of determining five resistance values and determining the static decay properties of each worksurface.

The wrist strap is the second major component of an ESD protective workstation and is used to ensure that static charges developed by the human body are safely carried away to ground. The wrist

strap consists of an adjustable, woven elastic fabric cuff and coiled, flexible ground cord. Stress testing of the cuff and cord was developed to best simulate stresses seen during normal use. Two pieces of equipment were designed and built at AGMC to stress both the cuff and the cord independently while monitoring the electrical resistance of each.

The common point ground system (CPGS) is the third workstation component and ensures that both the wrist strap and worksurface are connected to ground at the same point. This is important because it ensures that a wrist strap path to ground always exists. In the past the wrist strap and worksurface have been tied to ground at separate points on opposite sides of the worksurface and if the conductive path to ground within the worksurface became electrically open, then the wrist strap's path to ground would also be interrupted. The CPGS can be connected to either of two ground snap fasteners required on each worksurface at each end along their length. In the case of a type III (portable) worksurface, only one ground snap fastener exists. A one megohm current limiting resistor is also required within the CPGS in line with the worksurface ground path but not in line with the wrist strap since a one megohm resistor is required in the wrist strap cord itself.

Another important aspect of MIL-W-87893 is that it will standardize sizes of the CPGS, wrist strap, and worksurface snaps and ground connectors. It has been quite frustrating, in the past, to enter an ESD Control workarea and not be able to interchange the wrist strap or CPGS of one ESD workstation with the worksurface of another and vice versa. The requirements within MIL-W-87893 will allow for this to be done.

The major intent of the test methods explained within this paper are to allow for a means to ensure effective ESD Control Workstations are procured for use throughout DOD as well as to enable the wide variety of DOD employees who use the workstations to check their functionality over time. The resistance measurements explained within the text of this paper were chosen purposely as opposed to the commonly used surface resistivity measurements that are controversial, quite lengthy, sometimes unrepeatable and

inappropriate for most ESD control materials used in Military applications.

TEST METHODS

Worksurfaces

All worksurfaces to be tested per MIL-W-87893 must undergo some pretest preparations that include preconditioning in a dessicating chamber or controlled room for 24 hours at 20% ± 2% Relative Humidity (RH) and 70° ± 2° Fahrenheit (F). Prior to this, two cleanings of the sample worksurface with a 70% isopropanol-water solution (allowing one hour for evaporation of any remaining cleaning solution) is required. All resistance and static decay measurements must be done within 30 minutes of removal of the test sample from the dessicating chamber.

Test equipment used to make the resistance measurements of ESD Control Worksurfaces consists of two five-pound electrodes of 2.5 inch diameter and constructed as specified in ASTM F 150. Voltage is applied using a variable voltage megger with the capability of supplying a 500 volt DC open circuit test voltage and a measuring range of between 1 x 10⁶ and 1 x 10¹² ohms. Figure 1 is a photograph showing the electrodes and voltage source used for the resistance measurements.

Figure 1. ESD Worksurface Resistance Measuring Equipment

Five resistance values are determined for each four foot by two foot ESD Control Worksurface sample. These resistance values include resistance from the top of the worksurface to ground (R_{TG}), resistance from one point on the top of the worksurface to another point on the top of the worksurface (R_{TT}), volume resistance (R_{VL}), resistance through a ground snap fastener (R_{GS})

and current limiting resistor resistance (R_{CL}). Figure 2 summarizes these resistance measurements and specifies the limits of each resistance as called out in MIL-W-87893.

SUMMARY OF RESISTANCE MEASUREMENTS

Figure 2. Summary of Resistance Measurements

R_{TG} verifies that the resistance to ground is within a range such that when a static charge is placed on the surface of the ESD Control worksurface, it is carried away to ground in a time that is less than the time required for human movement and greater than the time necessary to create substantial discharge currents across the ESD sensitive devices that are to be protected. In addition, if the resistance is too low, personnel safety may be sacrificed. Figure 3 shows the placement of the electrode used for making this measurement. Note the three foot spacing from the ground point. This helps ensure that the conductivity of the worksurface has been maintained throughout its body. Worksurfaces that incorporate buried conductive layers could become electrically open across their width or length and measurements with the electrode at three inches or even one foot from the ground point may or may not bear this out. R_{TG} merely reveals whether the ground path is intact across the body of the worksurface. The limits of R_{TG} as specified in MIL-W-87893 are between 1 x 10⁶ and 1 x 10⁹ ohms.

ELECTRODE PLACEMENT FOR R_{TG}

Figure 3. Electrode Placement for R_{TG}

R_{TT} is the resistance or surface resistance between two points on the surface of the ESD Control worksurface. It is required so that surface currents can be controlled. Surface currents must be considered since they pose a threat to ESD sensitive circuits that may be on the worksurface. Figure 4 shows the electrode placement for R_{TT} . Note that two five-pound electrodes are used. The specified resistance for R_{TT} is between 1×10^6 and 1×10^9 ohms.

ELECTRODE PLACEMENT FOR R_{TT}

Figure 4. Electrode Placement for R_{TT}

R_{VOL} represents the resistance through the entire thickness of the worksurface. Many areas throughout the Air Force have metal workbenches for doing maintenance on electronic equipment where ESD sensitive items may be handled. If the worksurface to be used is too conductive or has a bottom layer (if layered) that is too conductive, then a parallel resistance path to ground has been established. This lowers the overall resistance to ground of the worksurface to less than the specified values. R_{VOL} as specified ensures that the static or current drain path is primarily through the current limiting resistor within the CPGS. Since R_{VOL} is required to be greater than R_{TG} and less than 1×10^{12} ohms (per MIL-W-87893), a majority of the static charge traveling to ground from the surface of the worksurface would indeed flow through the current limiting resistor. Figure 5 shows the electrode placement for determining R_{VOL} .

ELECTRODE PLACEMENT FOR R_{VOL}

Figure 5. Electrode Placement for R_{VOL}

The resistance of the ground snap fastener is represented by R_{GS} . Electrode placement for making this measurement can be seen in Figure 6. The ground snap fastener is simply a metallic connector used as a snap-on point for the CPGS and to ensure electrical continuity from the ESD Control worksurface to the CPGS. It passes entirely through the thickness of the worksurface. In most situations this resistance measurement would not be necessary, but when establishing requirements for ESD Control workstations that will operate in all or nearly all of the different working environments found within the Air Force, one condition necessitated this measurement and that is the use of metallic workbenches. Metallic workbenches are common throughout the Air Force. If the ground snap fastener, which typically passes through the body of the worksurface, comes in contact with a metal bench, the ground path for static charge coming in contact with the worksurface is now

directly to the bench and not through the current limiting resistor as designed. R_{GS} as specified has forced the static control vendors to place a layer of resistive material across the bottom of the ground snap fasteners. This required change in mat construction allows for the usage of the mats in all type of environment regardless of what the workbench is made of. This eliminates the need for the government to stock many different types of worksurfaces for many different kinds of working environments.

The current limiting resistor measurement, RCL, is a basic resistance measurement that simply ensures that the current limiting resistor exists within the CPGS in line between the ESD Control worksurface and ground. MIL-W-87893 requires that the current limiting resistor have a value of 1×10^6 ohms $\pm .2 \times 10^6$ ohms.

ELECTRODE PLACEMENT FOR R_{GS}

R_{GS} = GREATER THAN 1×10^7 OHMS
(MEASURED ONCE FOR EACH GROUND CONNECTION.)

Figure 6. Electrode Placement for R_{GS}

Electrostatic Decay testing is also performed on the three types of static dissipative worksurfaces. Static Decay testing determines the static charge dissipation rate of a worksurface material. Other published papers have discussed the limitations of decay testing such as its mistaken use as a triboelectric charging test, its inability to detect field suppression effects and other limitations. Many people also maintain that surface resistivity readings correlate well to static decay measurements. But this in fact is dependent upon construction of the material being analyzed as to whether the two methods can be correlated. The intent of determining the static decay rate of ESD Control worksurfaces in this instance is to find out how well it does correlate to worksurface resistance with such factors as preconditioning, sample size and electrode spacing being identical for each test method. As worksurfaces of different constructions are tested, relationships

between static decay and resistance are monitored. Thusfar, data suggests that static decay rates correlate well with the resistances discussed earlier. If this trend continues, decay testing could be eliminated from the specification in future revisions.

STATIC VOLTAGE DECAY (DISSIPATION) TEST SETUP FOR SOFT OR RIGID TABLE MATS AND PORTABLE WORKSURFACE

Figure 7. Static Voltage Decay Test Setup

Figure 8. Photo of Static Decay Test Apparatus

A schematic of the static voltage decay test setup can be seen in Figure 7 with a photograph of the equipment used for the test found in Figure 8. A 5000 volt DC current limited power supply is used to provide an initial 5000 volt charge to the

worksurface. A non-contact electrostatic probe connected to an electrostatic voltmeter is calibrated and used to ensure that the 5000 volt charge has indeed been applied to the worksurface and exists at a point three feet from the ground point. The decay time is determined with a recorder or oscilloscope connected to the voltmeter.

The decay time measurement is made by measuring the time required for the initial 5000 volt charge to decay to 50 volts after closing the grounding switch. Five static decay time measurements are made for a positive 5000 volt initial charge decayed to a positive 50 volts and five measurements for a negative 5000 volt initial charge decayed to a negative 50 volts. Each set of five readings are averaged to give an average positive and negative decay time for each worksurface tested. The specified time limit for both the positive and negative decay times is one second or less.

Wrist Straps

The wrist strap or personnel grounding strap consists of two basic parts. The first is an adjustable size wrist strap cuff made of a woven elastic fabric. It contains interwoven conductive threads so that electrical continuity is maintained about the wrist. The second wrist component is a five or ten foot coiled, insulated and flexible wrist strap cord that contains a 1 megohm current limiting resistor for personnel safety. The cuff and cord have specified male and female snap sizes, respectively. This is done to standardize snap connectors and allow for interchangeability of the cuff from one manufacturer with the cord of another.

The wrist strap cuff is stress tested by an apparatus constructed at AGMC. It was designed to subject the cuff to stretch testing similar to what is seen during normal use such as the employee motion of putting on and taking off the wrist strap. The test apparatus consists of a rotating shaft (2.00 inch swing radius) and a mounting bar which are both attached to a metallic T-shaped structure. Figure 9 shows the cuff stressing apparatus. The rotating shaft is driven by a 3 RPM motor which can be switched to rotate in both the clockwise and counterclockwise direction. MIL-W-87893 specifies that each new wrist strap cuff shall maintain a closed circuit resistance during this rotational stressing of between 1 and 10 megohms with the current limiting resistor connected in line to the wrist strap cuff. This resistance is required to be maintained for 3000 cycles in the clockwise direction and 3000 cycles in the counterclockwise direction. Upon test completion, conductive fibers that may have fallen from the stressed cuff are monitored. These conductive fibers are not desirable for operations where circuit boards are being repaired since they could short out the leads of components found on any particular board. The testing done here requires that no conductive fibers egress from the cuff.

Figure 9. Wrist Strap Cuff Test Apparatus

The wrist strap cord is also stress tested by an apparatus constructed at AGMC. It was designed to subject both ends of the cord to a flexing type stress that is commonly seen during normal use at an ESD protective workbench. The apparatus consists of a rotating disc and rocker arm assembly that is mounted on an L-shaped platform. Figure 10 provides a picture of the wrist strap cord stressing apparatus. Each sample wrist strap cord is mounted on the rocker arm assembly such that it is cycled continuously back and forth through a 120° arc. A motor drives the rocker assembly at a rate of 2000 cycles per hour. The resistance within the cord is monitored through a closed loop circuit that shuts off the drive motor when the resistance exceeds 10 megohms. A mechanical counter mounted below the apparatus' rotating disc measures the number of stress cycles completed. Each end of the wrist strap cord is required to withstand 16,000 cycles of stress.

The wrist strap cord and cuff are also required to dislodge from one another within a specified breakaway force range. This breakaway force should be great enough that the cuff/cord connection does not disengage too easily and less than an amount that could physically harm an operator who walks away from his/her static control workstation and forgets to disconnect the wrist strap cuff from the cord. The breakaway force requirement for the wrist strap cuff/cord connection is between one and five pounds as measured with a force gage.

The last two tests required of the wrist strap consist of a resistance to solvents test and resistance to salt test. Solvent resistance testing is done to both the wrist strap cuff and cord in accordance with MIL-STD-202, Method 215. Salt resistance testing is performed on the wrist strap

cuff in accordance with MIL-STD-202, Method 101, Test Condition A. Resistance to salt testing is important in that it simulates the effects that human perspiration may have on the wrist strap cuff and its electrical continuity. The electrical continuity of each cuff sample is checked after this test is performed.

Figure 10. Wrist Strap Cord Test Apparatus

Summary

The test methods and general construction requirements for ESD Control workstations presented in this paper are the first of their kind developed for use by the Air Force for the procurement of these workstations. The Air Force and other DOD organizations have purchased and still purchase many ESD Control Products based on information provided them by the manufacturer alone and consequently have received some products that are ineffective or unreliable.

The basic resistance measurements described for ESD Control worksurfaces represent techniques that are repeatable and can be done in both a product qualifying lab and by field personnel seeking to determine the effectiveness of their worksurfaces over time.

Static Decay measurements are taken so that correlations can be made with the resistance measurements mentioned above. Variations in worksurface construction and how they affect static decay measurements are information necessary to strengthen the need for resistance measurements only. Keeping critical factors such as preconditioning conditions, electrode and probe spacing, and sample size the same for both tests will aid in correlating the two methods.

Stress testing of wrist strap cuffs and cords is essential in ensuring that quality products are received by the Air Force. No previous stress testing of wrist straps was ever required and consequently, unreliable wrist straps were received. Other key performance requirements for wrist straps such as their resistance to solvents and salt, their breakaway force (cuff vs cord) and their contamination qualities, such as the egressing of conductive fibers, are required in MIL-W-87893.

The standardization of snap and ground connector sizes is accomplished within MIL-W-87893. A typical Air Force Maintenance facility that handles ESD sensitive items may have two or three different manufacturer's ESD Control workstations making it virtually impossible to interchange the ESD workstation components from one manufacturer's workstation with those of another. MIL-W-87893 will ensure that all manufacturers use the same sized snap and ground connectors.

Conclusion

MIL-W-87893 is a versatile specification that outlines acceptance test procedures for what is probably the most important item essential to effective ESD Control; the ESD Control Workstation. The test methods described in this paper are relatively simple, low cost and most importantly, they are repeatable. These represent the first in a series of requirements being written by AGMC as the AFLC ESD Technology Center for ESD Control Products. Government users of ESD Control Products have had no means of ensuring that the ESD Control Products they have procured in the past are effective and specifications such as this one will do that.

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